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DEMAND RESPONSE FLEXIBILITY: FORECASTS AND EXPECTATIONS FOR 2030 AND 2050

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Abstract

The change in the electric grid is a well-known and addressed topic. In order to achieve the very ambitious goals to prevent climate crises and to increase the participation of renewable generation without decreasing the reliability and security of the power system, demand side flexibility and demand response presents themselves as effective solutions to increase the needed flexibility. However, it is also necessary to make forecasts about the future of the system, which is more difficult for smaller loads in times of intense changes. This work addresses forecasts techniques and the predictions and expectations for achieving the net zero emission 2050 scenario with focus on the European market. Even though the scenario presents itself as very challenging, the efforts are being made and the rollout plans, in many European countries are advanced. Changes in policies will also need to take a faster pace in the next few decades.

Keywords: demand response; flexibility; forecast; 2030; 2050

1. Introduction

The electricity grid is changing and adapting to new restrictions imposed by environmental issues, and smart grids initiatives are also inducing the grid into a new scenario [1]. Another observable change is the increase of integrated community energy systems, which brings the benefits of CO₂ reduction and increase in efficiency and self-sufficiency [2] benefiting from smart grid technology and contributing with climate goals. However, in order to sustain this change, the grid is expected to get more resilient and cost efficient. For that, demand response (DR) programs are one solution to achieve the overall goal [1].

Nevertheless, an accurate methodology must be established in order to have a successful and trustworthy DR [3]. Furthermore, when aiming economic growth and environmental security in the future, electricity demand forecasting became imperative [4]. Even though large loads' forecasting (e.g., city, whole grid) has been demonstrating high accuracy in its results, smaller loads (e.g., building, community, micro-grid, houses) has been presenting a very prominent volatility in its dynamics. Besides that, data deficiency in what concerns users' information was pointed out as one of the main reasons DR programs fail to achieve its goals [1]. Thus, many techniques have been used for forecasting. Table 1 presents some of them.

Table 1: Forecast approaches

Name	Description
Time-series models	Simplest model Uses time series trend analysis for extrapolating the future energy requirement
Spline-based models	Avoid over-parametrization Rely on splines to describe the baseload

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Multivariate state-space models	Time-varying regression coefficients Useful for analyzing DR
Semi-parametric models	Predict the contribution of load from non-linear variables Useful for DR volume evaluation
Regression methods	Used to forecast different energy sources requirement (include electricity)
Econometric models	Correlate the energy demand with macroeconomic variables
Decomposition models	Energy consumption approach Energy intensity approach
ARIMA models	Extensively used
Artificial systems models	Benefit from artificial neural network Able to capture unspecified non-linear relationships between external variables like weather Criticized for leading to over-parametrized models Not necessarily outperform linear regression models Electricity load forecasting Long term energy demand projections considering macroeconomic variables
Grey prediction models	Simplicity Ability to characterize unknown system Need only a few data points
Input–output models	Access how social and economic changes affect energy requirements and energy intensity
Fuzzy logic/Genetic algorithm models	Fuzzy logic is used for short term electric load forecasting Modern computational techniques using genetic algorithms are being adapted for load forecasting
Integrated models	Some of the latest techniques (e.g., Bayesian vector auto regression) Support vector regression, ant colony, particle swarm optimization,... Used in energy demand analysis
Bottom-up models	MARKAL is a dynamic technique which was originally developed as a least cost linear programming model Long term energy demand and CO2 emission for China forecast using TIMES G5 model LEAP model is a bottom-up-type accounting framework which is used for forecasting

Adapted from [5]-[12].

Besides the evident need for forecasting, demand-side flexibility is becoming more relevant as countries take up more challenging climate goals. The power system transformation underway to support net zero goals is putting strain on both supply and demand, necessitating greater flexibility, which can increasingly be obtained through demand-side resources such as DR systems.

Lastly, this paper is organized in the following way. First, the introduction addresses demand response, demand forecasting and some issues and characteristics of the subject. The second topic addresses the methodology used in this research. The third topic covers DR forecasting considering different countries all over the globe. Followed by a section focused on the European scenario and, finally, the final section presents the conclusions of this work.

2. Methodology

For this analysis, two phases were conducted. The first one is a small introduction and review presenting the DR techniques available in the literature, its definition, and points of interest. The second one is a synthesis of the main demand response, demand response flexibility and smart meters information available. It was made in order to have a clear idea of what is expected and what is happening in reality. This second part was divided into two segments, global

and Europe, considering the characteristics of this research and the relevance and impact of European energy sector in the global scenario, besides its responsibility in addressing the climate crisis.

3. 2050 net zero emission and global expectations to achieve it

The Net Zero Emission by 2050 scenario (NZE), already mentioned, NZE refers to reducing greenhouse gas emission to as close to zero as possible to prevent the worst impacts of climate crisis [13]. Considering the fast pace required for the NZE, some assumptions/predictions were made based on what is necessary to achieve the ambitious goals needed to address the climate crisis. Based on that, Table 2 presents the expectations for 2030 and 2050.

Table 2. 2030 and 2050 expectations for NZE

2030	2050
have 500 GW of DR in the market	15% of average annual demand can be shifted to some extent
10 times increase (compared to 2020) of global inventory of flexible assets in all sectors (residential, commercial and industry)	fast implementation of more ambitious policies
further investments in smart grids are pointed as needed, however, no specific value is pointed out	fast electrification of transport, heating, and others
participation of electricity in the energy grid is also expected to increase to 26% (when compared to 20% in 2020)	experience a change in the demand curve shape
approximately 25% of total flexibility needed globally will come from battery storage and DR, especially in developed and developing markets	approximately 50% of total flexibility needed will come from battery storage and DR, especially in developed and developing markets
renewable participation on energy supply is expected to increase to over 60% (compared to 29% in 2020);	
double the electricity system flexibility	

Adapted from [14].

Based on that, the increase in renewable generation expected to 2030 are, already imposing the need for more flexibility in the energy system. Besides, one issue that may affect its development and the achievement of such goals is the need to increase information and communication technology. This increase can bring benefits as more quality data, real-time visualization, among others, but also bring some concerns as the risks associated with failures of these communication channels, security of supply and power system resilience [14],[15].

Finally, some steps are already being taken around the world in the direction of NZE 2050. Some examples are presented in Table 3:

Table 3. Actions per country

Country	Action
Australia	approved a wholesale DR mechanism, opening up the DR market to consumers and aggregators
Belgium	adopted a capacity remuneration mechanism that allows the participation of DR operators and is aimed at ensuring security of supply
Bosnia and Herzegovina	A project started with the installation of solar power plants on the roof of a primary school, with 25 kW capacity that 2 kW will be used for the needs of school and the rest will be directed to a power supply network that is enough for approximately 20 households

Chile	launched a power system flexibility strategy focused on market design, regulatory frameworks, and system operation
China	is in the process of issuing regulations on operations and ancillary services to encourage the use of storage, user-adjustable loads, load aggregators, virtual power plants and other resources in power system ancillary services
Colombia	extended tax incentives to non-conventional sources of energy and energy efficiency projects, including smart metering and DR
Singapore	is reviewing existing DR programs and schemes to improve remuneration methodologies, penalty and compliance rules
Slovenia	the main existing action to influence consumers' behaviour is the use of two different electricity prices, the high price 6 am to 10 pm, and the low price from 6 pm to 10 am (with adaptation during summer time)
United States	system operators in the six capacity and ancillary services markets were mandated to remove barriers to the participation of distributed energy resources of more than 100 kW, including DR, renewables, EVs and energy efficiency

Adapted from [6],[14].

Even with advances already started in several parts of the world, the challenges are so big, the goals so ambitious that it is very difficult to say that it would be achieved, and that it will reach/approximate to the NZE 2050 established scenario.

4. Current and expected European smart meters rollout

After summarizing global expectations, this topic will focus on the European situation and future scenarios. Considering the already addressed need of information and communication technology to achieve the level of DR flexibility required, this section will focus on European smart meters rollout evolutions and plans as a way to relate to demand side flexibility with prospects and future expectations. Figure 1 presents each country by its past, current and expected rollout.

From Fig. 1, it is also important to highlight some particularities of few countries [15]-[21]. Croatia and Slovakia, until now, did not present a positive rollout. Austria had a goal of achieving 80% by the end of 2020, however, only achieved 29% by the deadline. A similar situation happened with United Kingdom, the country had a 2019 as the deadline to achieve an 80% rollout rate, however, is only expected to achieve it by 2024. Finland, during the last years, became one of the main responsible for growth of smart meters in Europe. The French market for demand-side flexibility has grown by, approximately, 0.6 GW in 2021. In Germany, it is expected for the market to slowly expand until 2032. Italy is already halfway through its second-wave rollout of smart electricity meters and Sweden is also performing a large scale second-wave rollout. Based on that, one reason that may happen is the small presence of aggregators observed in European Union. The presence of aggregators could encourage, for example, the participation and attendance of prosumers.

Fig. 1 - EU rollout by country. Adapted from [15]-[21]. Note 1: Approximately 34.8 million smart electric meters units were installed in the bloc in 202. However, installations decline by 10% in 2020 due to COVID-19. Note 2: Some countries were not considered due to its dimension or not being part of European Union. Note 3: Norway was considered, even though it is not part of European Union.

So far, aggregators exist in 19 out of 28 MSs, as in the following graphic. However, according to [20], only eight European Union state members have aggregators able to operate autonomously from the supplier and only ten have residential consumers and aggregators are able to participate in the electricity market. Therefore, progress in policies would be crucial to improve this scenario, as pointed out in Table 3.

5. Conclusions

The reasons behind the need to adapt the energy sector as a whole and the electric sector in particular make it a global issue and an urgent one. Very ambitious goals were created with a challenging deadline. For that, forecasting the outcome is necessary to make new policies and to know the possible challenges in the future. During forecasts, the method is very relevant, but also is the data. Smart meters are a big deal in collecting users' data and allowing them to collaborate increasing the systems flexibility and reliability. That create a dynamic system with active roles from the generation to the end user. From this review and analysis, one can observe the urgent need for new policies implementation. Also, that most countries in Europe are in a fast pace to achieving the 80% rate on smart meter until 2024. Some countries had a bad start in 2020 but are expected to catch up during the 20's decade, which is very important considering the milestones for 2030. Finally, global and local efforts are being observed in the direction of NZE and, to achieve that, we will need more quality data to produce better forecasts, especially for local loads.

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